

An initiative of

 JACOBS
FOUNDATION

CAPTURING GUIDELINES FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY

Produced by

BACKGROUND

The Digital Museum of Learning is a global online museum for children and educators. It is an initiative of the Jacobs Foundation. The Digital Museum of Learning partners with museums, collections, and cultural institutions around the world to digitize their artifacts and artworks and bring them to life in interactive stories. Its online exhibitions are carefully curated collections of stories that explore the history and future of learning.

Lacking Standards for Cultural Heritage Digitization

As the Digital Museum of Learning embarked on its journey to digitize cultural heritage, we quickly realized that small and underfunded museums need help digitizing their collections. In addition, museums often rely on proprietary software solutions to digitize collections, which limits interoperability and accessibility for schools. We believe in harnessing the power of cutting-edge computer-aided imaging technologies, interoperability, and open access to digital cultural heritage. Our goal is to efficiently create high-quality, awe-inspiring 3D models and transform them into engaging and interactive experiences accessible to children and schools. In the future, cultural institutions will be able to use virtual and augmented reality technologies to create immersive and interactive experiences of historical sites and artifacts, allowing a global audience to engage with and gain a deeper understanding and appreciation of digitized cultural heritage.

Making Cultural Heritage More Accessible

In collaboration with museum partners and experts worldwide, we are charting a path toward a future where cultural heritage is more accessible to a broader audience, with a focus on schools. The mission of the Digital Museum of Learning is to empower educators and enable children to explore historical artifacts playfully and interactively, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of our diverse and shared history.

Anyone with an internet connection can access the digitized artifacts in the Digital Museum of Learning. The stories created around artifacts allow educators to use historical objects for learning activities without the need for a facilitator. This step in democratizing access to cultural heritage is especially important for marginalized communities who may have been historically excluded from participating in the preservation and sharing of their cultural heritage. Traditional methods of preserving and sharing cultural heritage, such as physical museums and archives, are limited by location, cost, and opening hours.

Preserving Cultural Heritage for Future Generations

Many physical artifacts and documents are at risk of deterioration, loss, or destruction due to factors such as natural disasters, human conflict, neglect, or lack of resources. Helping museums digitize these resources ensures that they are preserved in a format that can be easily reproduced and preserved for future generations to access and learn from.

Partner with the Digital Museum of Learning by contributing artifacts and resources. Together we can unlock the rich history and future of learning!

The Guidelines

These guidelines stem from a cooperation between the Digital Museum of Learning, researchers from the Digital Humanities Lab at the University of Basel, and experts from Virtual Culture GmbH. The Digital Humanities Lab at the University of Basel is a center of excellence in computer-aided imaging technologies. Virtual Culture digitizes, implements, and consults cultural heritage institutions and GLAMs (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums). Together, we created a 3D model of a botanical box from the collection of the Schulmuseum Bern, Switzerland for the Digital Museum of Learning (see: A box full of botanical adventures! www.museumoflearning.org). The process was documented in guidelines and accompanying videos. These guidelines describe the basics of close-range photogrammetry, a process used to create 3D models of small to medium-sized artifacts. They consist of two parts:

Part 1) [Capturing Guidelines](#) explore the process and necessary equipment to create high-quality images of an artifact (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7923606](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923606))

Part 2) [Processing Guidelines](#) describe how to generate a 3D model from these images using image-based modeling software (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7940422](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940422))

The guidelines were produced to facilitate the creation of digital cultural heritage for those who have not yet established a digital workflow in this area, as well as for museum partners and photographers, to help them capture, process, and deliver 3D models. For a more in-depth understanding of the showcase documentation, please refer to the accompanying video recordings for an easier and more accessible walkthrough:

Video 1) 3D Model Stage Preparation - PHOTOGAMMETRY (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.11259368](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259368))

Video 2) 3D Model Capturing - PHOTOGAMMETRY (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.11259651](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259651))

Video 3) 3D Model Processing - PHOTOGAMMETRY (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.11260493](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11260493))

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DISCLAIMER

The following guidelines for processing 3D models of cultural heritage objects describe the basics of digital photography and the specific techniques required to process the image files in image-based modeling (IBM) software. The guidelines are limited to the processing of small to medium-sized objects using a method known as close-range photogrammetry. These guidelines provide a general overview and are not intended to be a comprehensive solution for all types of cultural heritage objects or processing workflows. Suggestions for hardware and software are based on experience and do not reflect the personal or professional preferences of the individuals or institutions involved. They are only recommendations, not mandatory guidelines. Please note that the final selection and use of hardware and software is your own responsibility.

1. INTRODUCTION

Selecting an Artifact

An important step before beginning with the capture process is to identify the object you want to capture and determine if it is suitable for 3D modeling. The following are tips and things to keep in mind when choosing an artifact for 3D modeling.

- » **Size:** These guidelines address how to create 3D models of small to medium-sized objects. The larger the object, the larger the scene will need to be.
- » **Surface:** Transparent, highly reflective, or shiny surfaces, such as glass, glazed ceramics, mirrors or polished metals, or sparkly objects such as Christmas ornaments, can be tough to capture and are less optimal for creating a 3D model when using photogrammetry. Objects with heavily shadowed areas can be difficult to render as 3D models, as can objects with complex surfaces and details, such as fur or hair elements.
- » **Texture:** Textured objects are more interesting subjects for 3D modeling than objects that have a uniform surface or lack any structural detail.
- » **Shape:** It is easier to capture solid objects than objects that are hollow or have an opening. Objects with crevices or holes, such as a vase, or many curves or protrusions, such as sea urchins, are also challenging and require more images of the specific details.

2.1 COMPUTER

We recommend using a computer to remotely control the camera during the capture process. For this, you need a tethering cable. The computer you use for this step does not need to be capable of processing the 3D results, but it should have the following minimum specifications:

- » Processor: Intel Core i7 or i9, Apple M1/M2 or equivalent AMD Ryzen CPU
- » RAM: 16GB or more
- » Graphics card: Dedicated NVIDIA or AMD GPU with 4GB or more VRAM
- » Hard drive: 512GB
- » Free storage space: 100GB

If your goal is to process the model on the same computer you used to capture it (for example, if you have rented a computer for this purpose), please consult the Processing Guidelines, as processing the 3D model requires a more powerful computer than capturing (see: 3D MODEL PROCESSING GUIDELINES FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7940422](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940422))).

2.2 SOFTWARE

Remote camera control allows you to control your camera from a computer using a USB or tethering cable connection. With remote camera control software, you can easily adjust your camera settings, capture images, or view images on your computer screen as they are being captured. Using remote camera control can improve the quality of your images by preventing accidental motion blur, as a user can adjust settings and capture images directly from the computer without touching the camera.

The following applications are a few examples of software that allow you to control the camera settings and preview the image in a remote live view mode on your computer:

- » gPhoto (open source)
- » digiCamControl (open source)
- » Nikon Capture One
- » Adobe Lightroom
- » EOS Utility

Some software also provides features such as automatic file naming and interval capturing for image sequences, which makes it easier to process the images later. Automatic file naming is critical as it guarantees the unique identification of files. Interval capture allows for a continuous series of images.

When using remote camera control applications to capture images, it is important to review the image storage settings and specify the file format where you want to save or import the photos. Depending on where you decide to save or import the images, you will need to check the storage capacity and ensure you have at least 100 GB of space available for the images.

MAKE SURE YOU HAVE WHAT YOU NEED BEFORE YOU START CAPTURING:

- 1) COMPUTER
- 2) POWER ADAPTER
- 3) POWER CORD EXTENSION
- 4) PREINSTALLED SOFTWARE
- 5) TETHERING CABLE
- 6) CAMERA
- 7) BATTERY AND CHARGER
- 8) LENSES
- 9) LIGHTS (FLASHES AND SOFTBOX)
- 10) TURNTABLE
- 11) MATERIAL FOR HOMOGENOUS BACKGROUND
- 12) SCALE / PRINTED TARGETS
- 13) COLOR CHECKER

2.3 CAMERA

2.4 LENSES

DSLR Cameras

Use a digital DSLR or mirrorless camera with a resolution of less than 50 MP. The camera must have manual controls for aperture and shutter speed.

Camera Stand or Tripod

It is important to have a consistent camera setup and a stable platform for capturing images to ensure precise results. Use a stable camera stand or tripod that allows you to easily adjust the camera height.

Resolution

Photogrammetry does not require the same high resolution as standard photography. At pixel counts above 40 megapixels, processing time is significantly slowed due to the larger file sizes resulting from the large number of images required. In the interest of producing a high-quality 3D model, it is crucial to achieve sufficient overlap between images as opposed to relying on the resolution of a single image. A pixel count of 20 to 40 MP is sufficient.

Lense Specifications

We recommend using a lens optimized for close-up focusing and photography. Fixed focus macro lenses work well. In most cases, the distance between the camera and the object is only a few meters, so a lens suited to photographing at close distances is recommended.

If a fixed-focus macro lens is not available, use a wide-angle or standard lens (between 30 and 60 mm on a full-format camera). A wide-angle or normal focal-length lens allows you to capture a larger field of view, which is essential for capturing enough information to create accurate 3D models. Fixed focus lenses have minimal distortion and result in better image quality. If you choose to use an autofocus lens, optimize it by setting the focus to manual mode.

Aperture

Photogrammetry requires you to balance aperture size with the desire for greater depth of field and the need for a sharp image. For sharp images, we recommend using a medium aperture setting to minimize diffraction. It is generally recommended to use the widest aperture that still covers the depth of the artifact. Ideally, the aperture should only be adjusted to control sharpness. Exposure should be adjusted according to the intensity of the light source, such as a flash.

Lens Calibration

Some image-based modeling (IBM) solutions provide simple automatic lens calibration, which is required for each camera-lens pairing. Lens calibration is necessary to adjust the focus and alignment of a lens. Usually, automatic lens calibration software will prompt you to photograph a black and white pattern (target) from various angles. After importing the photos into the software, the software can detect distortion and focus inaccuracy. The software can then automatically make corrections or suggestions on how to properly calibrate your lens.

2.5 LIGHTS

2.6 TURNTABLE

2.7 TARGETS

2.8 SCALE

2.9 BACKGROUND

2.10 COLOR TARGET

Light Specifications

Use powerful studio lighting equipment with daylight quality and a color temperature of 5500K (D55). LED lights and xenon flashes work well. For larger artifacts or capturing in situations with a high level of ambient light, we recommend using more powerful strobe lighting (flash).

Light Exposure

When capturing an object through photography, it is crucial to prioritize its safety and well-being by ensuring proper care and conditions. The measure for harmful light is given in lux. The maximum value for light exposure is based on continuous light and assumes constant exposure to light. Fortunately, an object will not be damaged by strobe lighting (flash), even if it is powerful, due to the short duration of the light burst (usually <math><1/10000\text{ s}</math>).

The use of a manual or automatic remote-controlled turntable can be helpful in speeding up the capture process when capturing small objects. When using a turntable, the background, tripod, and camera position remain fixed (except for changes in height and vertical angle) while the object is rotated by the turntable. Examples of modern turntable systems include:

- » Syrp (Manfrotto)
- » Foldio 360 (Orangemonkie)
- » Puluz 360 (Puluz)

These turntables can be controlled remotely from mobile apps, the computer, or DSLR cameras via Bluetooth or infrared communication.

Coded markers are uniquely identified black and white patterns encoded in 12, 16, or 20 bits. They are automatically identified on the image files by the software. They provide the ability to scale the object and assist the software in estimating the position of the object relative to the camera.

"Light is the most important matter of photography. Make sure to use high quality light sources."

Scaling a 3D model is a crucial part of photogrammetry. It is important to take certain steps to ensure that the dimensions and proportions of the object are also captured during the photographic process. These steps ensure that the model can be scaled during processing in the IBM software. We recommend the following steps for a better capture of dimensions and scale:

- » For a size reference, place a calibrated ruler or scale bar in the scene and allow it to be captured along with the target object.
- » Measure the distance between characteristic points on the artifact for later reference.
- » Should any type of markers (e.g. manually added reference points) be placed on the scene, the distance between those markers can be used as well. With these measurements as a guide, the size of the 3D model can be adjusted to precisely match the dimensions of the actual artifact.

A uniform, evenly lit background is essential to the capture process. We recommend using a background or backdrop system that contrasts in color with the object.

If you do not have such a background system, make sure that the background is as homogeneous as possible. An uneven background can affect feature detection in the subsequent photogrammetry process.

"Use a background with enough contrast, that separates the artifact well."

Realistic Colors

Neutral and true-to-life color reproduction is essential for the accurate reproduction of artifacts. A color checker allows you to calibrate the colors in your images to match the actual colors of the scene. It also helps to ensure consistent color between different shoots, cameras, and lighting conditions.

Color Space

We recommend taking an initial image of the color checker for later calibration of the image data. The goal is high fidelity color reproduction in 3D space. The target color space is sRGB for all 3D workflows.

3. STAGE PREPARATION

ONCE ALL THE EQUIPMENT IS READY, SET UP THE SCENE, PAYING SPECIAL ATTENTION TO THE LIGHTING SITUATION:

- 1) Make sure there is no ambient light interference.
- 2) Illuminate the artifact with a standard D55 or D60 light.
- 3) Use large softboxes or a white capturing cube to evenly illuminate the artifact and reduce shadows. Alternatively, use a white wall or ceiling as a large reflector.

3.1 ILLUMINATION

Photographic images for 3D modeling do not have the same requirements as conventional photographs. In contrast to traditional photography, photogrammetric imaging aims to create a homogeneous and neutral image of the artifact. It is essential to reduce shadows on the artifact with lighting.

3.2 PERSPECTIVE

Perspective refers to the position of the camera relative to the object. Make sure the camera is set to capture the entire object. Details can be captured later. How you photograph the object often depends on its size. If the object is lightweight enough, we recommend using a turntable, which will rotate the object at intervals while the camera stays in a fixed position. The capture process is then repeated at different camera heights. When using a turntable, it is not necessary to reproduce the same angles with the turntable. In general, it is ideal to capture 30 different positions of

the rotating object at three different heights. Approximately 60% of the image should overlap from position to position. If an object has many detailed areas or areas that are difficult to access, such as ornaments or embossments, it is advisable to take additional detail shots so that there are no missing parts in the calculated model geometry and texture. If the object is small, lightweight, and stable, it should be photographed lying down or placed upside down to capture its base. These photographs of the different sides of the object can be combined in IBM software to create a complete 3D model.

4. CAPTURING

ONCE YOU HAVE SET UP YOUR EQUIPMENT AND PREPARED THE STAGE, THE NEXT STEP IS TO CONFIGURE THE CAPTURE SETTINGS:

- 1) It is important to understand that the captured images do not have to meet the aesthetic requirements of traditional photographic captures.
- 2) For the 3D modeling process, photographs can be thought of as surface measurements. The only requirement is that a maximum level of information about the object is provided. Therefore, it is usually necessary to slightly underexpose images to ensure that highly reflective parts are also captured with some structure.
- 3) Avoid overexposure. Overexposed areas of images do not provide any information about the color, shape, or texture of the object.

4.1 CAMERA SETTINGS

Exposure Mode

For reasons of exposure control and uniformity, it is essential to use the camera in manual mode (M). The shutter speed and lens aperture can only be set and locked in manual mode. This is important to ensure that all images are taken with the same exposure and depth of field.

Flash Sync Time

When using the strobe light (flash), the shutter speed must be synchronized with the flash speed. Be sure to set the camera shutter speed to the lowest possible flash sync speed (typically 1/250s for most SLR cameras). When handling the camera manually, be careful not to inadvertently change the exposure time.

File Formats

The ideal format for post-processing the images is the RAW file format with the camera's maximum quantization depth, such as 12 or 14 bits. Note that the RAW file format is not an archival master, but only an intermediate file format needed for post-processing. If your intent is to save the captured files for processing in other applications, save them as a TIFF or JPG2000.

ISO

A digital camera has a spectral sensitivity that is determined by the sensor and the electronics. For the best possible results and image detail for post-processing, we recommend using a low ISO setting

(<200). High ISO settings result in image noise and may reduce the quality of the final 3D model. Be careful not to set the ISO below the standard value (such as low -1), as lowering the ISO below this level limits the flexibility to make adjustments during post-processing.

AF

It is recommended that you turn off autofocus (AF), as you will need to manually control the focus for the capture process. Homogeneous surfaces with little or no structure can be particularly tricky and disrupt or confuse a camera's auto-focus system. This can lead to an accidental change in the plane of focus during a capture session.

4.2 EXPOSURE SETTINGS

Histogram

It is important to use the histogram to control exposure and avoid overexposure. If the contrast is too high, you can use fill light to reduce it. Fill light is best applied with large softboxes or indirect lighting, such as by using the walls of the room. Use fill light to reduce contrast.

Aperture

Lens aperture is key to determining the depth of field. When digitizing 3D objects, it is recommended to select an aperture between f/11 and f/22 for best results.

Using an aperture greater than f/22 results in a reduction in overall image sharpness due to optical diffraction. In photogrammetry, it is important to capture sharp images that accurately represent the full geometry of the object without blurring.

Shutter Speed Setting

We recommend using the shortest possible shutter speed that corresponds with the strobe (flash) speed. Using a shutter speed slower than the flash sync speed can result in incomplete exposure and may cause parts of

the image to be unlit. Generally, a flash sync speed of 1/250s is considered a safe and reliable choice for most cameras.

Sharpness

When it comes to capturing images for 3D modeling, it is critical to achieve optimal sharpness directly through the optical system settings. Post-processing sharpening techniques should be limited or avoided altogether. Excessive sharpening in post-processing can introduce noise and reduce the usability of the images for 3D modeling purposes.

4.3 FOCUS/FOCUSTACKING

In most capture situations, getting the artifact completely in focus or sharp is a challenge. Objects with a large spatial depth that extends beyond the camera's depth of field can be difficult to capture in high quality.

There are two solutions:

- » Capture multiple images with different planes of focus and process them in a second step with a focus stacking software such as TuFuse (freeware).
- » Use a tilt-shift lens to adjust the plane of focus.

4.4 COLOR SETTING

For compatibility with any post-processing software, we recommend using only the sRGB color space for image capture.

We recommend setting the default color rendering intent to Normal, Standard, or Neutral. This setting provides the best color reproduction for most cameras. Do not use a color target like the X-Rite Color-Checker, unless you are thoroughly familiar with creating custom camera profiles. Incorrect or inaccurate input color profiles can result in worse color accuracy than most built-in profiles.

5. IMAGE DATA PREPARATION

ONCE YOU HAVE ASSEMBLED THE EQUIPMENT, PREPARED THE SCENE, AND TAKEN THE IMAGES FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY, YOU NEED TO SAVE AND PREPARE THE IMAGE FILES FOR FURTHER PROCESSING:

- 1) Accurately name the images based on date and image position.
- 2) Save the RAW file as a backup.
- 3) Convert the files to TIFF or JPEG2000.
- 4) Check the exposure, sharpness, and overlap of the images.

5.1 NAMING

We recommend that you systematically name and organize your images as you capture them, as doing so will make it easier for you and others to find and classify them later. There is no specific rule for naming image files in image-based modeling software, but there are some recommendations you can follow. Filenames should include the date and the name of the object being captured. Format dates as "year, month, day" (YYYYMMDD). It is a good idea to end the filename with a number based on the position of the image, starting with 1, 01, or 001. If you made changes to the camera settings or took pictures from different angles, separate those images into different folders.

If there are many subfolders, save them in a subfolder with the date and object name in its filename. Do not use special characters such as periods, spaces, tabs, and line breaks.

5.2 DATA STORAGE

If your images were not saved directly to your computer during capture, you will need to transfer them from your camera to the computer. Store all files properly on at least two storage devices. Keep the RAW files until all processing is complete and the results can be viewed. Create folders for each capture session.

5.3 RAW CONVERSION

The RAW files (often .DNG or .NEF) should then be converted into a standard image file format such as TIFF or JPEG2000 using image processing software or image converters.

5.4 QUALITY CONTROL

Image quality control can be done automatically in most photogrammetry applications. Make sure the exposure is correct and do a quick visual inspection of the images. Check that the images are sharp, overlapping and properly exposed.

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Photogrammetry

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<https://www.capturingreality.com/>
<https://alicevision.org/#meshroom>
<https://www.regard3d.org/>

Modeling, Texturing, Rendering

<https://www.blender.org/>
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